

SOTERIA's first co-creation results on road safety

Unfolding VRUs' perspective on road safety across Europe

In 2023, SOTERIA project has proudly launched its Living Labs across four European countries on road safety for Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs). A central part of SOTERIA's research activities is the **co-creation process, directly including citizens into the design of technological solutions** to enhance road safety in complex urban environments.

Living Lab #1

Oxfordshire, United Kingdom

Safe and inclusive integration of micro-mobility to current mobility paradigms

Living Lab #2

Saxony, Germany

VRUs safety applications for generation Z

Living Lab #3

Madrid, Spain

Safe and shared mobility services for improving user well-being and clean urban

Living Lab #4

Chania/Igoumenitsa, Greece

Proactivity-based and micro-vehicle centric measures for unprotected VRUs

1st co-creation workshops in numbers

4 European countries

5 cities

Around **100** participants in all four Living Labs

More than **10** hours of total recordings time from participants' testimonies

Most represented road user group:

- cyclists
- children and adolescents
- elderly
- people with disabilities/wheelchair users
- powered two-wheeler drivers

Road safety issues and solutions based on participants' insights

Infrastructural Issues

Common issues across the Living Labs

Lack of well-designed cycle lanes

Poor road surface condition

Inadequate street lighting and signage

Accessibility issues for people with disabilities

Unique issues to each Living Lab

Oxford, UK Absence of underpasses at necessary intersections

Poor road design promoting car usage

Saxony, Germany

Madrid, Spain Inadequate urban infrastructure to accommodate increased mobility demands

Lack of infrastructure for wheelchairs and dangerous road conditions

Chania/Igoumenitsa, Greece

Road users' behaviour and attitude

Common issues across the Living Labs

Disregard for traffic rules and regulations

Lack of respect and consideration for other road users

Increased risk due to distractions and lack of situational awareness

Non-compliance with road safety norms

Unique issues to each Living Lab

Oxford, UK Disregard for safety among each road user group

Saxony, Germany Aggressive driving of motorists

Madrid, Spain Minimal situational awareness of road users in shared spaces

Chania/Igoumenitsa, Greece Non-compliance with traffic regulations

Technological assistance on the road

Common issues across the Living Labs

Use of navigation and routing software

Integration of smart navigation devices

Addressing accessibility challenges

Enhancing accessibility information and infrastructure

Unique issues to each Living Lab

Promotion of dash cameras

Recommendation for smart navigation devices on the handlebar

Detection system for scooters' generators and penalty enforcement

Redesigning routes for individuals with motor disabilities and wheelchair users facing unexpected problems

Proposed solutions to enhance road safety

Common proposed solutions across the Living Labs

Implementing comprehensive infrastructure upgrades and adaptations to improve road safety

Launching awareness campaigns and educational programmes to promote safer road use and compliance with regulations

Introducing advanced technological solutions aimed at enhancing road safety, including smart applications and AI-driven tools

Enforcing strict regulations and implementing measures to ensure compliance with safety standards and traffic laws

Unique proposed solutions to each Living Lab

Oxford, UK Implementing Dutch-style roundabouts to improve traffic flow and safety

Saxony, Germany Introducing temporary driving bans in front of schools to ensure the safety of schoolchildren

Madrid, Spain Standardising rules for micro-mobility to create consistency in regulations across municipalities

Chania/Igoumenitsa, Greece Compulsory purchase of helmets together with the purchase of motorcycles/bicycles to promote safety among riders